

**PHYSIOCHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF UYO VILLAGE ROAD DUMPSITE ON THE
MFANG MFANG STREAM IN AFAHA OKU, UYO, AKWA IBOM STATE, NIGERIA.**

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ABSTRACT

Solid waste management has remained a critical environmental challenge in rapidly urbanizing cities of Nigeria, with indiscriminate dumping posing significant risks to soil and water resources. This study investigates the physicochemical properties of leachate and water samples associated with the Uyo Village Road dumpsite and its potential impact on the Mfang Mfang stream in Afaha Oku, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The dumpsite, located in close proximity to residential areas and a surface water body, serves as a major disposal point for domestic, commercial, and municipal solid wastes, raising concerns about contamination and environmental health hazards. Water and soil samples were collected upstream, midstream, and downstream of the Mfang Mfang stream, as well as within and around the dumpsite. Standard analytical methods were employed to assess key physicochemical parameters including pH, electrical conductivity (EC), total dissolved solids (TDS), turbidity, dissolved oxygen (DO), biochemical oxygen demand (BOD), chemical oxygen demand (COD), nitrate, phosphate, sulphate, chloride, and heavy metals such as lead (Pb), cadmium (Cd), zinc (Zn), copper (Cu), and iron (Fe). Results were compared against permissible limits set by the World Health Organization (WHO) and the Nigerian Standard for Drinking Water Quality. Preliminary findings indicate that the dumpsite significantly alters the quality of adjacent water and soil environments. The pH values of leachate and downstream water samples tended towards acidity, while EC and TDS levels were considerably elevated, reflecting high ionic concentration and salinity. DO levels were notably low, whereas BOD and COD values were above acceptable limits, indicating substantial organic pollution. Nutrient concentrations were higher in downstream samples, suggesting eutrophication potential. Heavy metal analysis revealed concentrations of Pb and Cd above WHO limits, raising concerns about toxicity and long-term ecological and health risks. The study concludes that leachate migration from the Uyo Village Road dumpsite has adverse effects on the Mfang Mfang stream, impairing water quality and posing a threat to aquatic life and communities reliant on the stream for domestic use.

Keywords: *Physicochemical; Dumpsite; Pollutants; Waste Management; Environmental health.*

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INTRODUCTION

One of the prominent components of man's environment is river/stream that flows gently within its natural course. It serves as the source of water that man drinks. Other purposes such as agricultural and domestic are also servicing by water from the river/stream. Stream provides both defense and transportation mean for human beings, yet when the volume of water in it smells due to disposal of indecent elements such as waste it then starts to pose a threat to residents around its course. In order words, waste is seen as an unavoidable by-product of most human activities. Economic development and rising standard of living in Uyo and its environs have led to increases in the quantity and complexity of generated waste; whilst the provision of expanded health-care facilities have added substantial quantities of hazardous waste and biomedical waste into the waste stream with potentially severe environmental and human health consequences.

Rosenbaun (1994) observed that unregulated growth of urban areas and inadequate infrastructural facilities for collection, transporting, treating and disposal of waste have all contributed to increase in pollution. The heterogeneous mixture of plastics, cloths, metals and organic solution which are inevitable products of production and consumption are on increase as a result of urbanization that give room for indiscriminate discharge of solid and sewage waste into river channels thereby causing serious flooding which is a treat to life in general.

Wastes of different types, mostly solid wastes are the major input of dumpsites/landfills. Groundwater flows from areas of higher topography towards areas of lower topography, in the course of this degradable materials in dumpsites which form leachate flow in that wise and contaminate the groundwater of the study area. Dumpsite practice is the disposal of solid wastes by infilling depressions on land. The depressions into which solid wastes are often dumped include valleys (abandoned) sites of quarries, excavations, or sometimes a selected portion within the residential and commercial areas in many urban settlements where the capacity to collect, process, dispose of, or re-use solid waste in a cost-efficient, safe manner is often limited. The practice of dumpsite system as a method of waste disposal in many developing countries is usually far from standard recommendations (Mull, 2005; Adewole, 2009; Eludoyin & Oyeku, 2010). A standardized landfill system involves carefully selected location, and is usually constructed and maintained by means of engineering techniques, ensuring minimized pollution of air, water and soil and risks to man and animals. It involves placing waste in lined pit or a mound (Sanitary landfills) with appropriate means of leachate and landfill gas control (Alloway & Ayres 1997; Eludoyin & Oyeku 2010).

Leachate from dumpsites vary widely in composition depending on many interacting factors such as the composition and depth of waste, availability of moisture and oxygen, landfill design, operation and age. Groundwater refers to water which originates from the infiltration and percolation of precipitation through the soil profile and accumulates below the earth's surface in a porous layer commonly referred to as the aquifer. It forms part of the hydrologic cycle and the quantity and quality of water stored in the aquifer is a function of factors such as type of rocks, rainfall amounts, topography, surface cover and the state of the environment (Salami, 2012). When precipitation finds its way into a landfill, it

causes the extraction of water soluble compounds from the decomposed wastes thus forming garbage juice commonly called the leachate (Salami, 2012).

Land filling of municipal solid waste is a common waste management practice and one of the cheapest methods for organized waste management in many parts of the world (El-Fadel *et al.*, 1997; Jhamanani *et al.*, 2009; Longe & Balogun, 2010). Increasing urbanization results in an increased generation of waste materials and landfills become the most convenient way of disposal. Most of these landfills are mere ‘holes in the ground’ and do not qualify as sanitary means of solid waste disposal. Most of the areas around the Uyo village road dumpsites depend either on dug-up wells or bore-holes which may likely be affected by the generated leachate through waste decomposition from the dumpsites despite the provision of pipe-borne water by government. The leachate then seeps and percolates to groundwater aquifers thus causing groundwater pollution. The dumpsites contain domestic wastes, vegetable wastes, waste papers; scrap metals, cans for different chemicals, plastic containers, old rags, vehicle tyres, scalpels and human wastes. Some of these wastes are hazardous and are bound to cause serious health problems if they enter domestic water supply. Hence, it is on this background that the current research seeks to assess the Physiochemical properties of Uyo village road dumpsite on the Mfang Mfang stream in Afaha Oku, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

The present situation in Afaha Oku village in Uyo Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State and in several parts of Nigeria portrays the above described situation. Hence, the need for adequate and efficient waste disposal system in the research/study area cannot be over emphasized. Adequate and efficient waste disposal system is required for good health and neat environment. The effects of waste disposal and management in Afaha Oku village in Uyo Local Government Area has attracted the attention of various researchers whose studies were limited to waste management and effects of waste on underground water, on health status and visual intrusion. Waste disposed or flushed into the drainages and river courses in Afaha Oku village in Uyo Local Government Area engender major environmental problem, particularly, in Afaha Oku, being the major commercial centre of the entire study area. The bulk of waste generated in Afaha Oku and indeed Uyo metropolis are dumped into river courses which has led to a number of waste accumulation along the river courses and drainages resulting to water pollution, drainage blockage, infrastructural degradation, land pollution, flooding, erosion, leaching of pollutants into streams as well as spread of diseases like cholera, diarrhea, typhoid fever which are water-borne.

Attempts have been made by government to address the issue of waste collection and disposal within the study area. Such efforts involve creation of Local Government Waste Management Board by the State Government and recently sanitation department in the Local Government and Local Government Environmental Protection Agency (LGEPA), where Environmental Health Officers were directly involved in the past to supervise waste management of this area. However, empirical observation reveals that at the initial commencement by the waste management board, their services were effective due to the newness of its equipment especially with the assistance of the Niger Delta Development Commission (NDDC) in the supply of Dino trucks as well as the staff commitment to prompt maintenance of the waste equipment.

However, things started changing and took a new turn than later as in investigations revealed that this state of inefficiency as a result of insufficient Dino bins, poor maintenance of equipment, inadequate funding, greed, indiscipline, illiteracy and unconcerned attitudes from members of the public and official bodies that lead to inefficiency of effective waste management.

Study Area

Locational Extent

The study area is Uyo, the capital of Akwa Ibom State. Uyo is located at the central part of Akwa Ibom State and lies within longitudes 7°45'E and 8°05'E and latitude 4°50'N and 5°7'N. It covers a total area of about 200km. Uyo is bounded in the north by Itu Local Government Area, on the east by Uruan, South and West by Ibesikpo Asutan, and Abak Local Government Area respectively (Figure 1). It is situated on an elevation of about 60.96 meters (2090ft) above sea level (Njungbwen, 2011).

Figure 1.1: Uyo Showing the location of the Waste Dumpsite

Table 1.1: Water Quality Variables and their Standard Limits

S/N	Parameter	Units	WHO	NSDWQ
1	Temperature	⁰ C	25	NS
2	pH	NS	6.5-8.5	6.5-8.5
3	Electrical Conductivity(EC)	(μ Scm-1)	1000	1000
4	Total Suspended Solid(TSS)	Mg/L	3.0mg/l	NS
5	Total Hardness(TH)	Mg/L	100mg/l	150mg/l
6	Chloride(Cl-)	Mg/L	250mg/l	250mg/l
7	Nitrate(NO ₃ -)	Mg/L	10mg/l	50mg/l
8	Dissolved Oxygen(O ₂)	Mg/L	2.0mg/l	NS
9	Iron(Fe)	Mg/L	0.03mg/l	0.3mg/l
10	Lead(Pb)	Mg/L	0.01	0.01mg/l
11	Total Acidity	Mg/L	NS	NS
12	Total Alkalinity	Mg/L	200mg/l	NS
13	Sodium(Na)	Mg/l	200mg/l	NS
14	Phosphate(P ₀₄ -)	Mg/L	5mg/l	NS
15	Sulphate(SO ₃)	Mg/L	250mg/l	100mg/l
16	Copper(Cu)	Mg/L	0.5mg/l	1mg/l
17	Calcium(Ca)	Mg/L	200mg/l	NS

Source Nigerian Industrial Standard (2021)

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study adopted a cross-sectional survey design. From the perspective of the number of contacts with the object of study, the researcher adopted the comparative design for water quality analysis involving both the dry and rainy season and the cross-sectional survey design for questionnaire administration.

Types of Data

There are two types of data – quantitative and qualitative data. Both of these are equally important to this research project. Quantitative data is the value of data in the form of numbers where each data set has a unique numerical value. This data is any quantifiable information that researchers can use for mathematical calculations and statistical analyses to make real-life decisions based on these mathematical derivations.

Quantitative data is the data that approximates and characterizes. Quantitative data can be observed and recorded. This data type is non-numerical in nature. This type of data is collected through methods of observations, one-to-one interviews, conducting focus groups, and similar methods.

Sources of Data

The study used both the primary and secondary data. Primary data were collected through direct field survey. The data were collected from surface water samples around the

dumpsite and immediately taken to the University of Calabar, Oceanography Laboratory and Chemistry Laboratory for chemical, physical and heavy metals analyses. Analyses were carried out by lab attendants with author in attendance and results were obtained for interpretation.

Secondary data comprised of information from journals, articles, textbook and other publications. World Health Organization (WHO, 2004), Nigerian Standard for Drinking Water Quality (NSDWQ, 2007) standard limits and maps were also parts of secondary data utilized.

Sample and Sampling Techniques

Systematic random sampling of stream water samples with direct field survey methods was used for the gathering of data around the dumpsite in the last week of the month of May, 2025 and June 2025. The whole area of the dumpsite with a buffer zone of about 1km to the focal point of the dumpsite was sampled. Seven (7) surface water sample points were cardinally selected for the study including the control (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Location Map of Sampling Points

Surface water samples were collected with the aid of a distilled 10ml bottle water and the range of sampling were within the stream channel to the dumpsites sampled. Geographic coordinates (x,y,z) of all sampling points were identified through hand-held Global Positioning System (GPS channel 76CSx Garmin model), that measures in 2-3 m level of

accuracy. On the other hand, digital camera (Sony 14.1-megapixel model) was used at vantage point to take the aerial view of the dumpsites.

In the questionnaire administration, simple random sampling technique was adopted in selecting the sampled population using the sampled population of the project community (Afaha Oku).

Sampled Population

According to 1991 population census, Afaha Oku recorded a total population of 4127 with male comprising 1936 (46.9%) and female 2191 (53.1%). The 2022 projected population was 8605 at 3.5% annual growth rate. Meanwhile, the number of questionnaires administered was estimated using Taro Yamane formula.

Sample Size Estimation

Sample population was obtained using the Taro Yamane formula:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where;

n= Sample size, N = finite population of study area

e = level of significance (0.05)²

I = constant

$$n = \frac{8605}{1 + 8605(0.05)^2}$$

= 399. Approximately, 400

Techniques of Data Analysis

The obtained data was subjected to descriptive statistical analysis such as mean, standard deviation, coefficient of variation, graph, table, range as well as inferential statistics as summarized in Table 2.1.

Table 2: Technique of Data Analysis Based on Objectives

SN	Objective	Statistical Technique
1	To identify areas or locations where the stream water sources are vulnerable to pollution resulting from the presence of the dumpsite.	GIS/Mapping and One-Way ANOVA
2	To examines the seasonal variability in the level of pollution of Afaha Oku stream by the waste dumpsite	Independent T-test
3	Examine the impact of waste disposal on livelihood/health status of inhabitants of the study area.	Chi-Square
4	Measure and compare the difference in the quality of sampled water from Afaha Oku stream with World Health Organization (WHO) and Nigeria Standard for Drinking Water Quality (NSDWQ).	One Sample T-test

Results from water analysis was compared with those obtained by earlier researches in Calabar, Akwa Ibom and South-South and South-West zones to illustrate temporal variation of water quality parameters. Results will also be compared with World Health Organization (WHO 2004) and Nigerian Standard for Drinking Water Quality (NSDWQ 2007). The quality of water in surrounding areas of the dumpsites will further be analysed using the Contamination Index method and contamination levels of the area will be mapped.

According to Backman *et al.*, (1998), contamination index (Cd) may be considered as such if the measured concentration of parameters and the upper permissible levels of a contaminant is taken into account. Contamination index is defined as Eq. 1 and 2:

$$Cd = \sum_{i=1}^n Cfi \dots\dots\dots \text{Equation (1)}$$

$$Cfi = \frac{CA_{i-1}}{CN} \dots\dots\dots \text{Equation (2)}$$

Cd= contamination index;
 Cfi=contamination factor of the i-th component,
 CA_i = analytical value of the i-th component and
 CN_i=upper permissible concentration of the i-th component according to WHO standards.
 Contamination index (Cd) is calculated individually for each water sample, as a sum of the contaminant factors of single component that exceed the maximum contaminant levels (Ramos *et al.*, 2004). Therefore, Contamination Index summarizes the effects of several quality parameters that may be harmful to humans and the environment. The value scale for contamination index consists of 3 ranges; Cd < 1 (low contamination), 1 < Cd < 3 (medium contamination) and Cd > 3 (high contamination) (Edet *et al.*, 2002). Also, the spatial distribution of land use and degree of each parameter’s concentration in relation to sampling point was overlaid in maps.

Data Presentation

Table 3: Total Number of Administered Questionnaire

Number of administered questionnaires	Number of retrieved questionnaires	Percentage of returned questionnaire
400	388	97

Source: Researcher’s Field Work (2025).

In the survey, 400 questionnaires were administered out of which 388 were successfully retrieved at a returned rate of 97%. The demographic details of the respondents are presented in Table 3.

Demographic Background of Respondents

Table 4: Socio-Economic Data of Respondents

Data	Number of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Male	229	57.3
Female	159	42.7
Age:		
Below 20	32	8.2
21-30	83	21.4
31-40	107	27.6
41-50	108	27.8
51-60	35	9.0
Above 60	23	5.9
Marital status:		
Single	92	23.7
Married	156	40.2
Divorced	15	3.9
Widow	125	32.2
Education level:		
Non-formal	104	26.8
Primary	101	26
Secondary	91	23.5
Tertiary	50	12.9
Adult	42	10.8
Occupation:		
Farming	200	51.5
Trading	54	13.9
Civil service	24	6.2
Business	91	23.5
Others	19	4.9
Household size:		
Below 3	154	39.6
3—6	155	40
7—9	55	14.2
Above 9	24	6.2

Source: Researcher’s Field Work (2025).

Table 4 shows the demographic data of respondents. Pertaining to sex, the table explained that 229 respondents (57.3%) were male while 159 respondents (42.7%) were female. This

shows that the number of male respondents was greater than the female respondents. Concerning age, the table demonstrated that 32 respondents (8.2%) were below 20 years, 83 respondents (21.4%) were between the age of 21-30, 107 respondents (27.6%) were between 31-40, 108 respondents (27.8%) were between the ages of 41-50, 35 respondents (9.0%) were between 51-60 years while 23 respondents (5.9%) were between the age of 60 and above. This shows that a greater proportion of respondents were within the age of 41-50, followed by 31-40 before 21-30. This shows that mostly the youths are thoroughly engaged in sand mining activities. On marital status, the table explained that 92 respondents (23.7%) were single, 156 respondents (40.2%) were married, 15 respondents (3.9%) were divorced while 125 respondents (32.2) were widows.

Pertaining to education, the table put in plain words that 104 respondents (26.8%) have no assessed to formal education, 101 respondents (26.0%) has assessed to primary education, 91 respondents (23.5%) stopped at secondary level of education, 50 respondents (12.9%) luckily have been exposed to tertiary education while 42 respondents (10.80%) were engaged in adult education. This shows that the highest percentage of respondents were educated to the primary level, followed by those that have no assessed to formal education, before secondary, tertiary and adult education respectively.

With regard to occupation, the table shows that 200 respondents (51.5%) were farmers, 54 respondents were (13.90%) were traders, 24 respondents (6.2%) were Civil servants, 91 respondents (23.5%) were sand miners while 19 respondents (4.9%) belong to other occupation. Also, in relation to household size of respondents, the table clearly explained that 154 respondents (39.6%) have household size below 3, 155 respondents (40.0%) have between 3-6 household size, 55 respondents (14.2%) have household size ranging from 7-9, while only 24 respondents (6.2%) have household size above 9. this shows that majority of the respondents have household size between 3-6 followed by those below 3, 7-9 and above 9 respectively.

3.1.2 Income Distribution of Respondents

Table 5: Income Distribution Frequency of Respondents

Income	Frequency	Percentage
Below ₦20,000	73	18.81
₦20,000- ₦40,000	153	39.43
₦41,000- ₦60,000	78	20.10
₦61,000- ₦80,000	29	7.47
₦81,000- ₦100,000	24	6.19
₦100,000 and above	31	7.99
TOTAL	388	100.00

Source: Researcher's Field Work (2025).

Table 5 indicates the range of income of the respondents. It showed that 18.8% of the respondents earned below ₦20, 000. 39.4% earned between ₦20,000- ₦40,000 while

20.1% earned between ₦61,000- ₦80,000. The least number of respondents (7.49% and 6.19%) earned between ₦61,000- ₦80,000 and ₦811,000- ₦100,000 respectively.

Residential Distance from Waste Dump Site

Figure 3: Residential Area Distance from Waste Dump Site (Source: Researcher's Field Work (2025)).

Figure 3 shows that majority of the respondents (48%) are living between 2-4km from the dump site. However, 30% of them are living between 4-6km from the dumpsite, 12% are living more than 6km from the dumpsite while 10% of them are living less than 2km from the waste dumpsite.

Level of Engagement in Dumping Waste at the Dumpsite

Figure 4: Frequency of Engagement in Dumping of Waste (Source: Researcher’s Field Work (2025)).

Figure 4 shows that 50% residents of the area are involve in dumping waste at the dumpsite on weekly basis while 30% do so on daily basis. Only 9% carried out this exercise on monthly basis while the remaining respondents are rarely practicing carrying their waste to the dump but prefer burning and in few cases burying.

Load of Waste Dump

Figure 5: Frequency of Truck Loads of Waste Deposit (Source: Researcher’s Field Work (2025)).

This section was answered by people working at the waste dumpsite and they give an estimated number of trucks with dump waste at the site on daily basis. Figure 5 shows that on daily basis, 35% of the trucks that dump waste ranges from 11-30 trucks, 27% of are between 31-40 trucks. On the other hand, only 5% affirms it is above 50 trucks. It was added that the number of trucks that dump waste differs according to days but Saturdays mostly received the highest number of waste truck while Sundays and Mondays are the least. This implies that the maximum numbers of trucks of sand loaded per day ranges between 11-30 trucks.

Awareness of Negative Impact on Waste dumpsite

Figure 6: Awareness of the Negative Implication Waste dumpsite (Source: Researcher's Field Work (2025)).

As depicted in Figure 6, 88% of the residents of the area are aware of the negative consequences associated with dumpsite on their water quality while the remaining 12% are not aware. More so, all the residents are of the opinion that the waste dumpsite should be relocated for their best interest to safe the river from pollution.

Negative Impacts of Waste Dumpsite on Water Quality

Figure 7: Negative Impacts of Waste Dumpsite on Water Quality (Source: Researcher's Field Work (2025)).

Figure 7 indicates the level of negative impact of dumping along the stream. The negative impact includes: pollution of drinking water, loss of Spiritual and Aesthetic Value, spread of waterborne diseases, destruction of aquatic flora and fauna, threat to economic life of the people and siltation of the stream. As a result of this waste dump, the river ecosystem is under serious threat because of a break-in the food chain causing declining fish stocks, death of aquatic life, and destruction of aquatic flora and fauna. Furthermore, unsanitary conditions and water pollution due to the waste dump make the situation so dire that waterborne diseases are now widespread. The Mfang Mfang stream has lost its aesthetic values due to pollution as people are not comfortable with the foul odor from the river. Traditionally, this river has a religious significance to its rural communities and has a unique spiritual significance. Many people now feel uncomfortable bathing in the river due to pollution; evidence that pollution has prevented people from performing their religious rites.

Pollutants Level from dumpsite at different Distance

Figure 8: Pollutants Level from dumpsite at different Distances

Figure 7 shows that pollutant level decreases with increase in distance from the dumpsite. This implies that part of the stream closer to the dumpsite recorded more pollution level than places far from the dumpsite.

Table 6: Test for significant difference in the quality of a water sample in the area compared with the water quality standard of the WHO

SN	Parameter	WHO	T-Value	Mean	P-value	Decision
1	Temperature	25	5.97	30.62	0.000	Significant, higher
2	pH	6.5-8.5	-5.096	6.58	0.000	Significant, lower
3	Total Suspended Solid (TSS)	3.0mg/l	15.59	57.94	0.000	Significant, higher
4	Total Hardness (TH)	100mg/l	6.121	177.36	0.000	Significant, higher
5	Nitrate(N03-)	10mg/l	-2.266	8.51	0.041	Significant, lower
6	Dissolved Oxygen(O2)	2.0mg/l	-24.127	5.85	0.000	Significant, higher
7	Iron (Fe)	0.03mg/l	6.892	8.56	0.000	Significant, higher
8	Lead (Pb)	0.01	2.910	0.05	0.013	Significant, higher
9	Sodium (Na)	200mg/l	-326.21	0.6686	0.000	Significant, lower
10	Phosphate(P04-)	5mg/l	-22.160	2.19	0.000	Significant, lower
11	Sulphate(S03)	250mg/l	-774.58	1.7414	0.000	Significant, lower
12	Calcium (Ca)	200mg/l	-66.830	80.465	0.000	Significant, lower
13	Chromium	0.05mg/L	2.432	0.1794	0.030	Significant, lower
14	Cadmium	0.003mg/L	2.589	0.3964	0.022	Significant, higher
15	Nickel	0.02mg/L	-4.784	0.0144	0.000	Significant, lower
16	Magnesium	0.20	41.728	2.8836	0.000	Significant, higher
17	EC	1000	-18.967	224.90	0.000	Significant, lower

The result shows that across all the assessed parameters, there is a significant difference in the quality of a water sample in the area compared with the water quality standard of the World Health Organization (Table 6). This is because all the P-values were observed to be lower than the level of significant (0.05). interestingly, while some are below, others are above the WHO limits. For instance, parameters like Temperature, Total Suspended Solid (TSS), Total Hardness (TH), Dissolved Oxygen(O2), Iron (Fe), Lead (Pb), magnesium and Cadmium were all above WHO limits while pH, Nitrate(N03-), Sodium (Na), Phosphate(P04-), Sulphate(S03), Calcium (Ca), Chromium and Nickel were below WHO permissible limits.

RESULTS

The study examines the Physiochemical properties of Uyo village road dumpsite on the Mfang Mfang stream, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. The specific objectives include identifying areas or locations where the stream water sources are vulnerable to pollution resulting from the presence of the dumpsite. Examining the seasonal variability in the level of pollution of Mfang Mfang stream by the waste dumpsite, examining the impact of waste disposal on livelihood/health status of inhabitants of the study area as well as measure and compare

the difference in the quality of sampled water from Mfang Mfang stream with World Health Organization (WHO) standard.

Findings from the study shows that there is a significant difference in the effect of waste dump on water quality at different sections of the Mfang Mfang stream. At 30m distance from the dump, the mean pollutant level recorded highest followed by 50m while that of 150m and 500m recorded lowest contamination levels respectively. This is an indication that pollution level of the stream was so high in those sections closer to the dumpsites. Similarly, independent t-test analysis was conducted to check the seasonal variation in the level of pollution of Mfang Mfang stream by the dumpsite. The result shows that pollution level during wet season is slightly lower with a mean difference of 0.4309 but this variation is minimal and statistically insignificant. The result is in line with the work of Olaniyan, *et al* (2009) which noted that a number of dumpsites have been implicated for chemical and bacterial contamination of drinking water sources, in some cases, causing poisoning, cancer, heart diseases and teratogenic abnormalities. The migration and release of pollutants from waste dumps into streams pose a high risk to surface water users.

The result of the study also shows that there is a significant impact of waste dumpsite on livelihood/health of inhabitant of Afaha Oku community which ranges from pollution of drinking water to loss of spiritual and aesthetic value, spread of waterborne diseases, destruction of aquatic flora and fauna, threat to economic life of the people and siltation of the stream, among others. The result of this study is in line with the work of Ocheri *et al* (2008) which established a strong correlation between the degree of stream water pollution and the frequency of waste dumps in the stream environment. Toxic substances that have high concentration of nitrate, phosphorus and other pollutants derived from solid wastes can filter from a dumpsite and contaminate the stream waters. Similarly, Uting *et al* (2008) observed that pollution level and water associated infections in their study area were both proportional to the duration of exposure to contaminants. They noted that swimmers in the studied, polluted streams were exposed to pathogens, toxins and irritants that could easily enter the ears, eyes, nose and mouth as well as the anus and genitourinary tracks. In addition, they were exposed to a variety of other health problems including dermatitis and skin infections or deep tissue and blood infections through open cuts.

Similarly, the result of the study also shows that there is a significant difference in the quality of a water sample in the area compared with the water quality standard of the World Health Organization. Parameters like Temperature, Total Suspended Solid (TSS), Total Hardness (TH), Dissolved Oxygen(O₂), Iron (Fe), Lead (Pb), magnesium and Cadmium were all above WHO limits while pH, Nitrate(N₀₃-), Sodium (Na), Phosphate(P₀₄-), Sulphate(S₀₃), Calcium (Ca), Chromium and Nickel were below WHO permissible limits. The result corresponds with the work of Nazir, R. (2015) and Rastegari, M. (2015) that the presence of heavy metals in soil and water adversely affects soil microbes, ground, and surface water quality and ultimately becomes harmful to the health of humans in the food chain. More so, findings from this study agrees with the work of Lenntech (2019) that acid deposition has many harmful ecological effects when the pH of most aquatic systems falls below 6.0 and especially below 5.0. The work of Lenntech (2019) also added that low pH

could cause chronic stress that may not kill individual fish, but result in aquatic organisms having lower body weight, smaller size and make fishes less active to compete for food and habitat. The result matches with the work of Kumar *et al.* (2010) that cadmium has no essential biological functions in living organisms; its presence poses great threat to aquatic organisms especially, to fishes which is one of the major sources of protein rich food for human kind (Singh and Ajay, 2011). Sub-lethal effects in fish present in water sources, notable malformation of the spine as well as structural and function alterations in various vital organs including liver, kidney, gill and intestine have been reported (Kumar and Singh, 2010).

SUMMARY

In Uyo metropolis, an increase in urban population and the rising demand for food and other essentials perpetuate a rise in the amount of waste being generated daily by each household. Almost 80% of this waste is eventually thrown into open dump sites in Afaha Oku which is near a stream. It leads to severe impact on soil and surface water quality and as a result, it becomes the probable source of human health risk through food chain. This study however examines the Physiochemical properties of Uyo village road dumpsite on the Mfang Mfang stream, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. The specific objectives cover identifying areas or locations where the stream water sources are vulnerable to pollution resulting from the presence of the dumpsite. Examining the seasonal variability in the level of pollution of Mfang Mfang stream by the waste dumpsite, examining the impact of waste disposal on livelihood/health status of inhabitants of the study area as well as measure and compare the difference in the quality of sampled water from Mfang Mfang stream with World Health Organization (WHO) standard.

The result shows that pollution level during dry season is slightly higher than the wet season with a mean difference of 0.4309 but this variation was minimal and statistically insignificant. It also shows that there is a significant impact of waste dumpsite on livelihood/health of inhabitant of Afaha Oku community which ranges from pollution of drinking water to loss of spiritual and aesthetic value, spread of waterborne diseases, destruction of aquatic flora and fauna, threat to economic life of the people and siltation of the stream, among others. Similarly, the result of the study also shows that there is a significant difference in the quality of a water sample in the area compared with the water quality standard of the World Health Organization.

CONCLUSION

Hitherto, Mfang Mfang stream remains the major source of drinking water for residents of the community and its environs. This tradition remains for decades, not until the pollution of the water which all started from the dumping of waste from all over Uyo in that place. This study however shows an undoubted evidence of physical, chemical and biological pollutants in Mfang Mfang stream due to dumping of waste along the river bank. In spite some of the parameters tested for returned mean values, which were below the WHO limits for consumption, stream water pollution is still a serious problem that needs to be addressed because of the importance of streams as a major source of drinking water to so many communities and individuals in Afaha Oku and perhaps different parts of Nigeria.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In order to meet the Millennium Development Goal of clean and quality water supply in the study area, the problem of surface water pollution must be addressed. Thus, the following recommendations are made from the study:

- (i) Where stream water is used for drinking purposes, treatment (boiling, chlorination, etc.) is necessary in order to raise the stream water quality to a level where health risks are greatly minimized.
- (ii) Public awareness and enlightenment programmes on the dangers of indiscriminate dumping of wastes within stream environments and of drinking untreated water should be carried out in the Nigerian rural areas through participatory workshops, extension services, radio and television programmes etc.
- (iii) The rural communities should be motivated to develop and/or maintain alternative water supplies sources (deep wells, boreholes) through self-help activities.
- (iv) Governments should ban or discourage indiscriminate disposal of wastes within stream environments.

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